

CIMPAL-based assessment of cumulative biological pressures from invasive alien species, jellyfish blooms, and harmful algal blooms in the Italian Adriatic Sea

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ABSTRACT

Biological stressors increasingly threaten coastal and marine ecosystems. Invasive alien species (IAS), jellyfish blooms, and harmful algal blooms (HABs) are among the most widespread, yet their cumulative pressures are challenging to quantify. This study applies the Cumulative IMPacts of invasive ALien species (CIMPAL) index to assess the relative spatial patterns and intensity of these stressors in the western Adriatic Sea, drawing on validated observational and structured citizen-science data. Seven percent of the study area (4500km²) showed cumulative pressure, with higher CIMPAL scores in coastal than offshore waters and spatially localised rather than widespread patterns.

Hotspots were found in the northern and central Adriatic Sea, mainly due to the co-occurrence of IAS and jellyfish blooms while HABs were more restricted to lagoons and deltas. Non-parametric tests revealed significant spatial differences among Adriatic sectors. These results reflect potential cumulative pressure rather than measured ecosystem degradation and highlight the value of incorporating citizen science data while acknowledging its limitation. Findings support integrated, multi-stressor management under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD).

1. Introduction

Human activities are significantly altering marine ecosystems, leading to unprecedented changes in ecological processes (Holman et al., 2025) and harming human health (Tsirintanis et al., 2022; Lloret et al., 2024). Key drivers of these disruptions include the spread of non-indigenous species, climate change, overfishing, eutrophication, and the rise of jellyfish blooms (Boero et al., 2016; Smale et al., 2019; Tempesti et al., 2020a, 2020b).

Biological invasions are among the most severe human-induced disturbances. Since the 19th century, the introduction and establishment of alien species have accelerated and are expected to intensify in

the 21st century, especially in the Mediterranean Sea (Costello et al., 2022; Zenetos et al., 2022). By 2020, 1006 non-native marine and brackish-water species had been recorded in this region (Galanidi et al., 2023). Some of these species are already highly invasive, affecting native biodiversity, community structure, habitats, and ecosystem functioning in sensitive areas (Katsanevakis et al., 2016; Navarro-Barranco et al., 2018; Morri et al., 2019; Tsirintanis et al., 2023). Their impacts range from reduced fitness of native species to population declines, local extinctions, and shifts in community composition (Katsanevakis et al., 2014).

Climate change, overfishing, and the construction of artificial barriers and permanent coastal structures have also contributed to jellyfish

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proliferation, with consequences for plankton communities and food-web dynamics, as well as for fisheries, aquaculture and tourism (Purcell et al., 2007; Boero, 2013; De Donno et al., 2014; Bosch-Belmar et al., 2020). Major blooms such as those of *Pelagia noctiluca* in the early 1980s (Morand and Dallot, 1985; Malej and Malej, 2004; Sabatés et al., 2010) or *Mnemiopsis leidyi* in the Black Sea during the 1990s (Kideys, 1994; Shiganova, 1997) have demonstrated how strong outbreaks can disrupt fisheries and trophic structure contributing to a shift toward jellyfish-dominated ecosystems (Mills, 1995, 2001).

Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) are likewise increasing worldwide under warming and nutrient enrichment (Anderson, 2014; Wells et al., 2015; Glibert and Burkholder, 2018; Glibert, 2020), generating impacts on marine biota, human health (Shumway et al., 2018; Wells et al., 2020; Tsikoti and Genitsaris, 2021; Zingone et al., 2021; Sagarminaga et al., 2023; Accoroni et al., 2024a, 2024b; Sardo et al., 2020; Tsikoti and Genitsaris, 2021; Tsikoti and Genitsaris, 2021, 2021, 2021) as well as aquaculture and fisheries (Roselli et al., 2019; Marampouti et al., 2021).

Human ability to predict the effects of anthropogenic pressures on marine ecosystems, particularly with respect to ecological tipping points and regime shifts, remains limited due to their complexity (Hemraj and Carstensen, 2024). For these reasons, an ecosystem-based management (EBM) approach should ensure that combined pressures from land and sea activities remain within levels compatible with Good Environmental Status (GES) under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, 2008/56/EC) (EU, 2008), particularly considering climate change (Franco et al., 2025). This approach helps marine and coastal ecosystems remain resilient to human-induced changes and supports the sustainable use of marine resources for present and future generations.

Specifically, the MSFD requires EU Member States to develop national strategies and implement measures to achieve GES in European marine waters. GES is defined by eleven qualitative descriptors, each with specific assessment criteria. Among them, Descriptor 2 (“Non-indigenous species”, NIS) entails Member States to address alien species in their marine management strategies, ensuring that NIS introduced through human activities are at levels that do not adversely alter the ecosystems. Invasive alien species directly affect other descriptors, including Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity) and Descriptor 6 (Seafloor Integrity). Jellyfish and species potentially causing HABs are addressed under Descriptor 1, Criterion 6, and Descriptor 5 (“Eutrophication”), Criterion 3. Thresholds for these groups, particularly regarding GES, remain undefined due to limited data. Ecological imbalances from jellyfish blooms impact fisheries and food webs (Lynam et al., 2006), making them relevant to Descriptor 3 (Commercial fish and shellfish) and Descriptor 4 (Food webs), and indirectly, to eutrophication and biodiversity loss. Nutrient enrichment and climate change have increased the frequency of HABs, threatening water quality, ecosystem health, and public safety. Effective monitoring and management are essential for achieving GES across Descriptors 1, 3, 4, and 5 (Katsanevakis et al., 2023; Sagarminaga et al., 2023, 2024).

In this context, spatial cumulative assessment provides tool for identifying hotspots of biological pressure and understanding where management efforts are most needed. While several cumulative impact frameworks exist (e.g., Halpern et al., 2008), the CIMPAL index (Katsanevakis et al., 2016) is particularly suited for IAS driven pressure and allows integration with jellyfish and HAB data.

With this study, we aim to:

1. Update current knowledge on the presence and distribution of IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs in the western Adriatic Sea (Italian Waters).
2. Assess the cumulative impact of IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs in the study area using the CIMPAL index.
3. Identify the most heavily affected areas and ecosystem components using spatial analyses and standardised datasets, including monitoring, research and citizen science sources.

2. Methods

2.1. Study area - The Adriatic Sea

The Adriatic Sea (AS) is a semi-enclosed basin located in the North-Central Mediterranean Sea, which spans approximately 64,500km² (Fig. 1). It is connected to the Eastern Mediterranean Sea through the Strait of Otranto. It separates Italy from the Balkan Peninsula, and borders six countries: Italy, Slovenia, Croatia, Montenegro, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Albania. The surface water exhibits a marked seasonal temperature cycle, with peak values in late summer and maximum mixed-layer depths in winter. The northern AS exhibits the typical characteristics of a shallow sea, with significant seasonal variations in temperature and salinity and strong vertical stratification. The central AS serves as a transitional zone, characterised by deep-water persistence during spring and summer and by a persistent middle Adriatic gyre. The southern AS, especially below 150m, exhibits open-sea characteristics, with traces of Modified Levantine Intermediate Water detectable in its subsurface layers and, to a lesser extent, in the central basin.

The western AS is characterised by a highly complex system due to its geomorphological and ecological characteristics: lagoons, estuarine areas, coastal habitats of high biodiversity (e.g., sandbanks, *Posidonia oceanica* meadows, coralligenous assemblages), and deep-sea habitats, with high variability along its north-south gradient. Moreover, it is populated by benthic, demersal and pelagic fish species of high ecological and commercial value.

Several rivers flow into the AS, providing a source of nutrients and organic matter to the basin (Sfriso et al., 2021), as well as litter and microplastics (Liubartseva et al., 2016). Therefore, the western Adriatic coastal waters are among the most productive in the Mediterranean Sea (Giani et al., 2012). The Italian AS is heavily exposed to anthropogenic pressures (Coll et al., 2012; Menegon et al., 2018) and is also a hotspot for biological invasions, particularly in the northern sector (Occhipinti-Ambrogi et al., 2011; Marchini et al., 2015; Chiesa et al., 2025). Due to its wide, flat, and sandy-muddy platform, coupled with high productivity, the AS is the Italian basin with the highest fishery pressure and historically one of the most exploited areas in the Mediterranean Sea (Fortibuoni et al., 2017; Marguin et al., 2025). Other potential sources of ecological disturbance are coastal urbanisation (the coastal population is > 3.5 million people), commercial and recreational shipping, offshore platforms from the oil and gas industries, aquaculture, coastal tourism, and recreational activities (over 200 million overnight stays per year), including poor waste management practices (Fig. 2).

2.2. Records of IAS, jellyfish blooms and HABs

For the CIMPAL index calculation, we decided to consider all available IAS data in the western AS, starting with their first record, because some of them, recorded in earlier periods, may still be present even though they are no longer reported in the literature (Table 1).

Georeferenced data for these species, spanning 1949 to 2024, were obtained from datasets developed in research programs and from the literature (Tables 1 and 4 in Supplementary Materials). To avoid conceptual overlap among stressor categories, organisms were classified using explicit criteria. IAS were identified based on established Mediterranean and European reference lists (Zenetos et al., 2022; Galanidi et al., 2023) and international databases (AquaNIS, EASIN). Only taxa whose non-indigenous status is broadly accepted in the literature were included. In contrast, jellyfish blooms and HABs were considered biological pressure events, generated by native or non-native species with a documented capacity to cause ecological or health-related impacts in the western AS. HAB taxa were selected according to evidence of toxin production in the Mediterranean, irrespective of biogeographical origin, whereas jellyfish species were included based on recurrent bloom events and their recognised ecological effects.

Fig. 1. Western Adriatic Sea: spatial coverage of the study (in colour online). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

This extension of the CIMPAL framework allows integrating multiple biological pressures into a unified cumulative-pressure assessment. The CIMPAL assessment included jellyfish species with documented impacts on the pelagic habitat of the western AS (Table 1). Most jellyfish records were sourced from the CIESM Jellywatch (CIESM, 2001) and Avvistapp campaigns, both available on the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) platform (Boero et al., 2019; Tirelli and Goruppi, 2021). Additional data came from the Meteo Meduse Facebook page, launched in 2016, and the citizen science platform iNaturalist (inaturalist.org) (Tables 1 and 4 in Supplementary Materials). All projects engaged citizens in a jellyfish visual census and followed the CIESM jellywatch protocol (Boero et al., 2008; Edelist et al., 2025), which required the date, genus or species, location, abundance (individuals per square metre), and a photograph for each observation. Sightings were compiled in a database, and those with more than ten individuals per

square metre were classified as blooms. Only records verified by a photograph were included. Visual census observations from the Territorial Environmental Protection Agencies (ARPAs) (MSFD (D1)) were also added (Table 1 and 4 in Supplementary Materials).

Some of the HABs data used in this study, covering the period 2016–2021, were also obtained from Italian MSFD monitoring activities conducted by the ARPAs in the AS and follow the shared methodologies adopted for comparing results under Descriptor 1 Biodiversity – Pelagic Habitat. Phytoplankton samples were collected at the surface or down to the Deep Chlorophyll Maximum along transects perpendicular to the coastline, at stations located 3, 6, and 12 nautical miles offshore. These stations correspond to those used to monitor physical–chemical variables and nutrients. Sampling frequency was monthly or bimonthly, depending on the trophic status of the waters. In addition to MSFD monitoring, we also considered data from the national surveillance

Fig. 2. Overview of biological stressors and human pressures in the AS (in colour online).

program for potentially toxic microalgae conducted under the Bathing Water Directive (BWD), with particular reference to *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* (2016–2023) (ISPRA, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024). Monitoring was carried out by the ARPAs during the summer season under optimal temperature and hydrodynamic conditions. The sampling sites are located in coastal areas and were selected based on prior evidence of the presence and/or maximum proliferation of the species (Table 1 and 4 in the Supplementary Materials). Among the species found in the AS, only those listed in Table 1 were considered for the CIMPAL evaluation, according to Chiappi et al. (2025) (Table 1 and 4 in the Supplementary Materials). HABs were included based on their documented HABs formation or toxin production with ecological or health-related impacts (DSP) in the western AS.

Biomass indices for some benthic species (Table 1 and 4 in the Supplementary Materials) were derived from the Mediterranean International Trawl Survey (MEDITS; MEDITS working group, 2017) and the Solea Monitoring Project (SOLEMON) (Scarcella et al., 2019). These are scientific bottom trawl survey programs using a standardised otter trawl (MEDITS) that covers the entire AS and a modified beam trawl (SOLEMON) that covers the northern and central AS.

2.3. Ecosystem components

The ecosystem components considered in this study included marine seabed habitats classified according to the EUNIS system (Vasquez et al., 2023), as obtained from the EMODnet Seabed Habitats Portal. These habitats were subsequently regrouped, according to the environmental features (e.g., fraction of surface light reaching the seabed, seabed type) of the AS, into the broader categories proposed by Tsirintanis et al. (2023) and revised (Tab. 2 in the Supplementary Materials).

Each of the eight identified seabed habitats was then overlaid onto the study area's 3km × 3km polygon grid to calculate the area covered by each habitat within each cell (Hj index). ΣHj of each seabed habitat in each cell is equal to 1, except for the cells straddling the shore and the sea, where the sum is < 1.

The pelagic habitat was included in the CIMPAL calculation because jellyfish and HABs affect the water column. These phenomena are particularly relevant as they can significantly influence the abundance of small pelagic fish by preying on their eggs and larvae, thereby affecting their recruitment and population dynamics (Oguz et al., 2008; Purcell et al., 2007, 2015; Boero, 2013; Palmieri et al., 2014; Bosch-Belmar et al., 2020).

Table 1

List of IAS, jellyfish and species related to HABs for the taxonomic group included in the CIMPAL index calculation in the western AS.

IAS	
Macrophyta	<i>Acrothamnion preissii</i> , <i>Asparagopsis</i> spp., <i>Bonnemaisonia hamifera</i> , <i>Caulerpa cylindracea</i> , <i>Codium fragile</i> , <i>Gracilaria vermiculophylla</i> , <i>Grateloupia turuturu</i> , <i>Lophocladia lallemandii</i> , <i>Polysiphonia morrowii</i> , <i>Rugulopteryx okamurae</i> , <i>Sargassum muticum</i> , <i>Undaria pinnatifida</i> , <i>Womersleyella setacea</i>
Porifera	<i>Paraleucilla magna</i>
Ctenophora	<i>Mnemiopsis leidyi</i>
Arthropoda	<i>Acartia tonsa</i> , <i>Callinectes sapidus</i> , <i>Dyspanopeus sayi</i> , <i>Rhithropanopeus harrisi</i>
Polychaeta	<i>Ficopomatus enigmaticus</i> , <i>Hydroides elegans</i>
Mollusca	<i>Anadara kagoshimensis</i> , <i>Anadara transversa</i> , <i>Arcautula senhousia</i> , <i>Fulvia fragilis</i> , <i>Magallana gigas</i> , <i>Mya arenaria</i> , <i>Ruditapes philippinarum</i> , <i>Bursatella leachii</i> , <i>Rapana venosa</i>
Bryozoa	<i>Amathia verticillata</i> , <i>Tricellaria inopinata</i>
Ascidacea	<i>Botrylloides violaceus</i> , <i>Microcosmus squamiger</i> , <i>Styela plicata</i>
Fish	<i>Enchelycore anatina</i> , <i>Fistularia commersonii</i> , <i>Lagocephalus sceleratus</i> , <i>Pterois miles</i>
Jellyfish	
Hydrozoa	<i>Aequorea forskalea</i> , <i>Olinidia muelleri</i> , <i>Porpita porpita</i> , <i>Velevella velevella</i>
Scyphozoa	<i>Aurelia</i> spp., <i>Carybdea marsupialis</i> , <i>Chrysaora hysoscella</i> , <i>Cotylorhiza tuberculata</i> , <i>Pelagia noctiluca</i> , <i>Rhizostoma pulmo</i>
Thaliacea	<i>Salpa maxima</i> , <i>Salpa</i> spp.
HABs	
Dictyochophyceae	<i>Vicicitus globosus</i>
Dinophyceae	<i>Ostreopsis ovata</i> , <i>Dinophysis</i> spp., <i>Karenia brevis</i> , <i>Karlodinium</i> spp.

2.4. CIMPAL implementation

The CIMPAL index was applied to assess and map the effects of IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs in the study area (Fig. 1).

The CIMPAL index was calculated for each 3km × 3km cell of the study area. For the IAS, jellyfish blooms and HABs, this was accomplished by applying the following formula:

$$I_c = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m A_i H_j W_{ij}$$

I_c refers to the Cumulative impact score in a specific cell of the study area; A_i represents the population state of species i in the cell, H_j is an index representing the extent of habitat j in the cell; w_{ij} is the impact weight of species i on habitat j , n is the total number of species, and m is the total number of marine habitats considered in the analysis. Specifically, for IAS and HABs, A_i values were expressed as species presence (1) or absence (0). In contrast, jellyfish blooms were assigned using the scoring system described by Chiappi et al. (2025), which considers both bloom intensity and the total annual duration of blooms. The H variable was standardised to a range of 0 to 1.

The w_{ij} values for IAS, jellyfish blooms and HABs were derived from the scoring system provided by Tsirintanis et al. (2023), which estimates the impact weight as a combination of the magnitude of the effect of species i on habitat j and the strength of supporting evidence.

The H_j index was calculated as the percentage of the area covered by a specific habitat within a 3km² cell of the study area. The H_j value of the pelagic habitat, due to its spatially continuous covering, was considered equal to the sum of H_j indexes of seabed habitats within each grid cell.

The final CIMPAL index was calculated for each of the 7,432 grid cells in the study area by aggregating the cumulative impacts of IAS, jellyfish blooms and HABs.

Furthermore, following Katsanevakis et al. (2016), four indicators were used to rank the species based on their negative impacts:

- Species occurrence Area (D1): Total number of grid cells with at least one record of the species.

- Impact area (D2): Number of grid cells where the species' impact score exceeded 0.
- Cumulative impact scores (D3): Summed impact scores across all cells.
- Average impact score (D4): Mean impact score across the species' range of occurrence, excluding cells with scores below 0.1.

Finally, to compare the CIMPAL index score across geographical areas, the Kruskal-Wallis rank-sum test was applied, followed by pairwise post-hoc comparisons using Dunn's test with Holm's adjustment for multiple comparisons (ggstatsplot package; Patil, 2021). Differences were considered statistically significant when p-values (Holm-adjusted for post-hoc tests) were <0.05.

Beyond statistical significance, the magnitude of the observed differences was assessed through the estimation of effect sizes using epsilon-squared (ϵ^2). This measure indicates how much of the variability in CIMPAL scores can be attributed to the geographical grouping factor. Following commonly accepted guidelines (Cohen, 1988), ϵ^2 values of approximately 0.01, 0.06, and 0.14 were interpreted as representing small, medium, and large effects, respectively.

2.5. Preparation of layers for calculating the CIMPAL index scores

The CIMPAL index scores dataset was created using the geo-processing toolset and the Analysis Toolbox in ArcMap 10.3.

Species occurrences point layers (for IAS, HABs, and jellyfish blooms) with attributes W_{ij} and A_i , respectively, associated with each species and occurrence, were geometrically intersected (using an identity function) with the study area polygon grid, which contains H_j information in each cell. This process produced the CIMPAL index score for each cell, which was then joined back to the study-area grid.

The resulting CIMPAL index score dataset for each biological component was aggregated to produce the maps of cumulative impacts of IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs.

The Getis-Ord G_i^* hot spot analysis (GOG*), implemented in the ArcMap Spatial Statistics toolbox, was also applied to the CIMPAL index scores, both for total CIMPAL scores and specifically for those related to IAS and jellyfish blooms. This method was used to detect statistically significant clusters of high (hot spots) and low (cold spots) CIMPAL values, identifying areas of concentrated cumulative impacts based on the spatial configuration of the data. It does not introduce artificial values in unsampled areas, thereby preserving the discrete nature of the original dataset and ensuring that the identified patterns are statistically robust rather than visually inferred (ESRI, 2025).

2.6. Grid resolution and spatial data harmonisation

The spatial resolution of the analysis (3 km × 3km grid) was defined after evaluating the native spatial characteristics and positional uncertainties of the input datasets. The CIMPAL framework integrates data from standardised trawl surveys (MEDITS, SOLEMON), institutional monitoring programs (MSFD, Bathing Water Directive), literature and citizen science initiatives, which differ in sampling design, spatial coverage, and effective spatial support. Therefore, the selected grid size was intended to reflect the intrinsic spatial resolution of the dominant data sources while avoiding artificial over-precision in the representation of species occurrences. To assess the robustness of the spatial patterns to grid size, a sensitivity analysis was conducted by recalculating the CIMPAL index using alternative spatial resolutions (1km, 5km, and 10km). The 1km grid generated highly fragmented patterns, largely influenced by localised observation clusters, whereas the 10km grid produced substantial spatial smoothing, reducing the ability to discern ecologically meaningful hotspots. The 3km grid represented the most balanced solution, preserving spatial detail while ensuring stability and consistency of cumulative impact patterns at the basin scale. Regarding uneven monitoring effort, we acknowledge that coastal areas,

particularly in the northern and western Adriatic, are more intensively monitored, which may increase the detection probability of IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs. However, the structure of the CIMPAL framework reduces sensitivity to raw reporting density. First, the index is not based on observation counts but on species presence within spatial cells combined with habitat-specific impact weights ($w_{i,j}$). This approach limits the influence of local reporting frequency compared to abundance- or density-based metrics. Second, integrating multiple independent data streams (standardised surveys, institutional monitoring, and citizen science) reduces reliance on any single source of observations. Offshore sectors, although less represented in citizen science initiatives, are covered by standardised survey programs (e.g., MEDITS/SOL-EMON), ensuring basin-wide spatial representation. Third, hotspot detection was performed using the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic, which evaluates spatial clustering relative to neighbouring cells rather than absolute values alone. Consequently, isolated cells with high reporting effort are unlikely to generate statistically significant hotspots unless supported by spatially coherent patterns.

3. Results

3.1. Cumulative impact scores for IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs

Cumulative impact scores for IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs per grid cell ranged from 0 to 16 across the entire study area. A total of 511 cells had values greater than 0 (6.9% of the study area), with a mean (\pm standard deviation) of 2 (± 2). Coastal areas exhibited significantly higher cumulative impact scores than offshore waters, with impacts being spatially localised rather than widespread (Fig. 1 in the Supplementary Materials). Higher-impact areas were more common in the northern and central AS than in the southern region (Fig. 3), with total CIMPAL index scores of 241, 183, and 87, respectively (Tab. 3 in the Supplementary Materials). These patterns largely reflect the occurrence and co-occurrence of IAS and jellyfish blooms in highly used coastal areas. Because CIMPAL is based on presence-only observations, low or zero values in some grid cells may partly reflect limited sampling rather than true ecological absence.

Among the habitats considered, the pelagic environment was most

Fig. 3. Zoomed-in views: Spatial variations of cumulative impacts of invasive alien species, jellyfish blooms, and harmful algal blooms in the Northern, Central and Southern Italian sectors of the AS using CIMPAL index scores. Data classified using a manual classification method (in colour online). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

affected, followed by shallow soft substrates and lagoons. This pattern reflects both the extensive spatial coverage of pelagic habitats and the high frequency of jellyfish bloom records, which affect pelagic waters. In some areas, IAS were the primary contributors to cumulative pressure, while jellyfish blooms dominated the pelagic component, followed by invasive ctenophore *M. leidyi*. In contrast, the bivalve *M. gigas*, a benthic species in its adult stage, contributed primarily to pressures on shallow soft substrates, together with *Anadara* spp., *A. senhousia*, *M. gigas*, *R. philippinarum*, *R. venosa*, and *C. sapidus*. In lagoons, IAS macroalgae (e.g., *A. preissii*, *G. vermiculophylla*, *R. okamurae*, *S. muticum*) and the polychaete *F. enigmaticus* contribute substantially to cumulative scores.

The GOG* hot spot analysis (Fig. 4) revealed a highly significant hot spot in the Venice Lagoon, as well as along the coasts of Ravenna, Rimini, and the Conero Promontory (99% confidence). Significant cold

spots (99% and 95% confidence) were detected along the coastline between the Conero and Gargano Promontories. These clusters align with areas of intense maritime traffic and aquaculture, suggesting a role of anthropogenic drivers (Fig. 4). These spatial patterns show a pronounced heterogeneity in the distribution of cumulative impacts along the western AS. Because the analyses rely on aggregated grid cells, spatial patterns are partly influenced by observations density and cell size, and low-impact areas may coincide with sectors where sampling was sparse.

3.1.1. Cumulative impact scores for IAS

Cumulative impact scores for IAS ranged from 0 to 15.5 (Fig. 2 in the Supplementary Materials), with the highest values occurring in areas subjected to intense propagule pressure from shipping routes and

Fig. 4. Hot spot analysis (Getis-Ord G_i^*) on CIMPAL index scores: Map of the GOG* for invasive alien species, jellyfish blooms, and harmful algal blooms in the western AS. Areas with statistically significant spatial clustering (cold spots—blue gradient; hot spots—red gradient) are shown. Yellow indicates non-significant index values (in colour online). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

aquaculture activities. A total of 318 cells showed values greater than 0 (4.3%), with an average (\pm standard deviation) value of 3 (± 2). The northern AS is the sector most affected by IAS (Fig. 5), with the highest total CIMPAL index score (534). In contrast, the southern sector has the lowest index value (total CIMPAL index score = 62) (Tab. 3 in the Supplementary Materials).

The GOG* hot spot analysis on IAS CIMPAL index scores (Fig. 6) revealed a highly significant hot spot in the Venice Lagoon, as well as along the coasts of the Conero Promontory (95% and 99% confidence, respectively). In contrast, cold spots (90% confidence) were detected north of the Conero Promontory and further south within the study area. The presence of large areas with no significant GOG* values (Fig. 6) indicate pronounced spatial variability in IAS-related cumulative impacts along the Italian Adriatic coastline. In contrast, the hotspots identify two localised areas of high pressure, revealing clear spatial clusters and emphasising the heterogeneous distribution of biological

invasions across the region. As with the aggregated results, IAS scores reflect potential pressure patterns based on species presence, and areas with low scores may lack observations rather than IAS impacts.

Among the most widespread IAS, *A. transversa*, *A. kagoshimensis*, *M. leidyi*, *C. sapidus*, and *R. venosa* exhibited the broadest distribution according to D1. Twenty-three out of forty-one IAS showed an impact on at least one habitat. When considering the number of impacted cells (D2), the highest-ranking species were *M. leidyi*, *C. sapidus*, and *A. transversa*. The D3 cumulative impact scores identified *M. leidyi*, *A. transversa*, and *M. gigas* as the most impactful species. Finally, D4, which accounts for the average impact score across each species' range of occurrence, ranked *R. okamurae*, *C. cylindracea*, *R. philippinarum*, and *W. setacea* as the most impactful IAS in the study area (Fig. 7).

3.1.2. Cumulative impact scores for jellyfish blooms

Cumulative impact scores for jellyfish blooms ranged from 0 to 4.0

Fig. 5. Zoomed-in views: Spatial variations of cumulative impacts of invasive alien species (IAS) in the Northern, Central and Southern Italian sectors of the AS using CIMPAL index scores. Data classified using a manual classification method (in colour online). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 6. Hot spot analysis (Getis-Ord G_i^*) on CIMPAL index scores: Map of the GOG* for invasive alien species (IAS) in the western AS. Areas with statistically significant spatial clustering (cold spots—blue gradient; hot spots—red gradient) are shown. Yellow indicates non-significant index values (in colour online). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

across the entire study area (Fig. 3 in the Supplementary Materials; Fig. 8). A total of 322 cells showed values greater than 0 (4.3%), with an average value (\pm standard deviation) of 0.6 (\pm 0.6).

The northern AS has the highest total CIMPAL index score of 106, while the southern sector has the lowest (total CIMPAL index score = 26) (Tab. 3 in Supplementary Materials). Because jellyfish data derive largely from presence reports, numerical differences among sectors should be interpreted as potential pressure patterns rather than as measured ecological impacts.

The GOG* hot spot analysis of CIMPAL index scores derived from jellyfish bloom impacts (Fig. 9) revealed a highly significant hot spot along the coastline between Ravenna and Rimini (99% and 95% confidence), as well as in the Gulf of Manfredonia (95% confidence) (Fig. 9). Cold spots were detected along the coastline between the Gulf of Trieste

and the Venice Lagoon, as well as farther north of the Conero Promontory (Fig. 9). These spatial patterns highlight localised clusters of elevated or reduced cumulative pressures and indicate clear spatial gradients across the western Adriatic.

The total area of occurrence (D1) and the number of cells with an impact >0 (D2) coincide, as all jellyfish taxa contributed to impacts in the western AS (Fig. 10). Among the most widespread species, *R. pulmo*, *C. marsupialis*, *Aurelia* spp., *C. tuberculata* and *P. noctiluca* exhibited the broadest distribution according to D1.

Based on D3, the highest cumulative impact scores were for the same species group, while according to D4, *P. noctiluca* ranked highest (Fig. 10).

Fig. 7. Ranking of IAS impacts in the AS: The figure shows the results for indicator D1 (left panel) and indicators D2 (top right), D3 (middle right), and D4 (bottom right) (coloured online).

3.1.3. Cumulative impact scores for HABs

Cumulative impact scores for HABs ranged from 0 to 5 across the entire study area (Fig. 11). A total of 64 cells exceeded 0 (4.3%), with an average (\pm standard deviation) of 2 (\pm 1). Because HABs data are more spatially heterogeneous and sampling intensity varies considerably among regions, patterns must be interpreted cautiously: low impact areas may result from low reporting effort rather than the true absence of HABs.

The total area of occurrence (D1) and the number of cells with an impact >0 (D2) coincide, as all HABs were identified as impactful in the AS (Fig. 12). Among the most widespread species, *Dinophysis* spp.

exhibited the broadest distribution according to D1. Based on D3, the species with the highest cumulative impact scores were *Dinophysis* spp. and *O. ovata*. According to D4, *O. ovata* ranked highest.

3.2. Comparison of CIMPAL index scores among the Northern, Central, and Southern sectors of the western AS

The Kruskal–Wallis test revealed a significant difference in the aggregated CIMPAL index scores (including IAS, jellyfish, and HABs) across the three geographical sectors ($p < 0.05$, $\chi^2 = 31.12$); Fig. 13). Post-hoc Dunn tests with Bonferroni adjustment correction showed that

Fig. 8. Zoomed-in view: Maps of cumulative impacts of jellyfish blooms in the Northern, Central and Southern sectors of the western AS using CIMPAL index scores. Data classified using the Natural Breaks (Jenks) classification method (in colour online). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

the Northern sector exhibited significantly higher median value (median = 2.37) compared to both the Central (median = 1.00) and Southern sector (median = 0.87), confirming a clear north-south gradient.

Analyses for each stressor demonstrated that this gradient was driven exclusively by IAS (Figs. 4–6 in the Supplementary Materials).

Specifically, IAS CIMPAL scores differed significantly among sectors ($p < 0.05$, $\chi^2 = 19.26$; Fig. 4 in the Supplementary Materials), with the Northern sector showing the highest median value (median = 3.33), significantly exceeding those observed in the Central (median = 1.97, $p < 0.05$) and Southern sectors (median = 0.93, $p < 0.05$). Conversely, no significant spatial differences were detected for jellyfish blooms or HABs (Figs. 5 and 6 in the Supplementary Materials); numerical differences were present but not statistically significant after correction and should therefore be interpreted cautiously given the limited input data and the heterogeneous sampling.

4. Discussion

The Cumulative Impact Assessment from IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs reveals pronounced spatial heterogeneity across the AS, with a clear north-south gradient. The northern area shows markedly elevated values due to intense maritime activities, major river mouths, aquaculture facilities, and extensive urbanisation, which have long been associated in the literature with altered nutrient regimes, modified habitats, and an increase in IAS introduction (Boero, 2001; Zampardi et al., 2025; Tsikoti and Genitsaris, 2021).

While our data indicate a spatial co-occurrence between cumulative pressures and these anthropogenic gradients, causal mechanisms such as nutrient enrichment or fisheries exploitation cannot be directly inferred from the present analysis and should therefore be interpreted as potential associations rather than explicit drivers. This interpretation aligns with long-standing evidence of ecological vulnerability in the northern Adriatic, historically linked to eutrophication, warming, hypoxia, overfishing, mucilage events and recurrent planktonic blooms (Degobbis et al., 1986; Solidoro et al., 2010; Fortibuoni et al., 2010;

Fig. 9. Hot spot analysis (Getis-Ord G_i^*) on CIMPAL index scores: Map of the GOG* for jellyfish blooms in the western AS. Areas with statistically significant spatial clustering (cold spots—blue gradient; hot spots—red gradient) are shown. Yellow indicates non-significant index values (in colour online). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Zingone et al., 2021).

Approximately half of the IAS considered in this study were associated with high cumulative impact scores combining broad spatial distributions with strong local ecological effects. High-risk species such as *M. leidy*, *A. transversa*, and *M. gigas* displayed elevated scores across the CIMPAL components, reflecting their distribution patterns and known ecological plasticity (Smith et al., 2014; Dolmer et al., 2014). Other IAS with more restricted distributions—but high D4 values—such as *R. okamurae*, *C. cylindracea*, *R. philippinarum* and *W. setacea*, exert substantial localised pressure through mechanisms documented in the literature, including nutrient cycling alterations, displacement of native functional groups, or changes to substrate properties (Bartoli et al., 2001; de Caralt and Cebrian, 2013; García-Gómez et al., 2021; Lopes et al., 2018; Piazzini and Cinelli, 2000; Ruitton et al., 2011). Due to the

severity of its impacts, *R. okamurae* has also been included in the list of Invasive Alien Species of Union concern (Union List) (Regulation 1143/2014) since July 2022 (European Union, 2022). The distinction between widespread species with moderate impacts and localised species with severe effects highlights the value of impact-based assessment frameworks.

Jellyfish blooms showed relatively uniform impact across the AS, although localised hot spots were detected in the northern area between Ravenna and Rimini. These areas align with previously described favourable areas for jellyfish proliferation due to productivity patterns, hydrographic structure, and coastal features supporting polyp stages (Boero, 2013; Purcell et al., 2015). However, specific mechanisms such as reduced small pelagic fish abundance and biomass or nutrient-driven increases in gelatinous zooplankton, were not directly tested in this

Fig. 10. Ranking of jellyfish blooms impacts in the western AS: The figure shows the results for indicators D1, D2 and D3 (left) and for indicator D4 (right) (in colour online). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

study and should be considered plausible but unverified processes (Cury et al., 2000; Zampardi et al., 2025; Cacciamani et al., 2025). Species such as *M. leidy* and *P. noctiluca* pose particular concern due to their well-documented predation on eggs and larvae of small pelagic fishes (anchovy and sardine), potentially triggering cascading effects on fisheries (Morello and Arneri, 2016) and ecosystem resilience, underscoring the need for adaptive management strategies that account for jellyfish as a recurrent stressor (Benović et al., 1984; Shiganova and Malej, 2009; Reyes Suárez et al., 2022; Zampardi et al., 2025).

HABs exhibited more spatially restricted patterns but potentially substantial local impacts as reflected by their comparatively high average D4 scores. Recurrent blooms of *O. ovata*, and *Karolodinium* spp. in hotspot areas of the central and southern Adriatic are consistent with previous observations linking these species to warming, nutrient enrichment, substrate availability, and hydrodynamic stability (Accoroni et al., 2012; Sardo et al., 2020). Although their overall spatial footprint (D1) was limited, the severity of local impacts reinforces the need for targeted monitoring in ecologically sensitive or socioeconomically relevant coastal areas. The spatial restriction of HABs compared to IAS and jellyfish suggests that localised drivers, such as nutrient hotspots and hydrodynamic retention zones, should be explicitly considered in predictive models and management plans.

The consistency between CIMPAL index distribution and known environmental and anthropogenic gradients suggests that stressors may co-occur non-randomly; however, the extent to which these pressures interact synergistically cannot be determined from these data alone. This reinforces the need for integrated EBM and multi-pressure approaches aligned with the MSFD and EU Biodiversity Strategy.

This methodological innovation strengthens the case of participatory science as a complementary tool in marine programs to mitigate socio-economic risks, particularly in areas of high tourism, aquaculture, or ecological value (Mannino et al., 2021; Marambio et al., 2021; Gueroun et al., 2022; Compagnone et al., 2024; Zenetos et al., 2024; Edelist et al., 2025; Zampardi et al., 2025), although its use introduces potential biases due to uneven spatial coverage, higher reporting in touristic areas, and variability in observer expertise.

Despite its strengths, this study has some limitations: first, data availability and quality varied among taxa and regions, and presence-based datasets cannot capture establishment success, population

dynamics, or functional impacts. Second, although citizen science observations are valuable, they cannot establish causality. Third, the spatial resolution of the grid may obscure fine-scale ecological processes, particularly in highly heterogeneous coastal habitats. Finally, the CIMPAL index score quantifies potential pressure based on documented impacts but does not directly measure ecosystem functioning, such as productivity, biogeochemical cycling, or trophic network stability. Future research should integrate the present assessment with mechanistic and predictive models incorporating climatic, hydrodynamic, and anthropogenic drivers to anticipate bloom dynamics and IAS spread.

Coupling these models with harmonised monitoring protocols and early warning systems would enhance preparedness and resilience. Integrating functional indicators and validating citizen-science observations through coordinated monitoring networks will further improve the robustness of cumulative impact assessment. Overall, combining participatory and traditional approaches represents a promising avenue for strengthen adaptive EBM and supporting MSFD implementation.

5. Conclusion

This study provides the first basin-wide, integrated assessment of the relative cumulative pressure exerted by IAS, jellyfish blooms and HABs in the western AS. By applying the CIMPAL index, we identify spatial patterns and coastal hotspots of potential biological pressure, offering a preliminary but robust basis for prioritising management attention under the MSFD. These results highlight areas of relative risk, but not quantified ecological degradation, and should therefore be interpreted as guidance for surveillance.

Our findings underscore the need for targeted surveillance, early warning systems and harmonised monitoring protocols to address multi-pressure dynamics. While this assessment is descriptive and presence-based, it provides a useful framework for integrating different biological pressures and informing risk-aware management actions.

Future work should couple these spatial insights with predictive models and functional ecosystem indicators to enhance resilience, support adaptive management and contribute to achieving GES in the region.

Fig. 11. CIMPAL index score-based assessment of HABs impacts: Map of cumulative impacts of HABs in the western AS. Data classified using a manual classification method (in colour online). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Ethics statement

Data were obtained from public monitoring programs, validated citizen-science observations, and published literature. All citizen-science data complied with privacy regulations and were collected with informed consent. Permits were not required because only observational records and secondary sources were used. The research adhered to ethical standards for scientific integrity and data transparency.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Serena Zampardi: Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Resources, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Patrizia**

Perzia: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Resources, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Tiziana Cillari:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Resources, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Luca Castriota:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Resources, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Emanuela Spada:** Data curation, Resources, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Patrizia Borrello:** Data curation, Resources, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Danilo Scannella:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Manuela Falautano:** Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Teresa Maggio:** Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Giulio Farella:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Writing

Fig. 12. Ranking of HABs impacts in the western AS: The figure shows the results for indicators D1, D2 and D3 (left) and for indicator D4 (right) (in colour online). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 13. Comparison of cumulative IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs impacts across Italian Adriatic sectors: Violin plot comparisons of CIMPAL index scores for IAS, jellyfish blooms and HABs across the AS sectors (North, Central, South). Violin plots show kernel density distributions; boxplots (inner rectangles) display quartiles; red dots indicate median values; coloured dots represent individual observations. Kruskal-Wallis test statistics (χ^2 , p-value) and epsilon-squared (ϵ^2) effect sizes with 95% confidence intervals are displayed within each panel. Horizontal bars with p-values indicate statistically significant pairwise differences (in colour online). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

– review & editing. **Giuseppe Scarcella**: Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Laura Sabatini**: Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Tomaso Fortibuoni**: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2026.108237>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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